

Isocoumarins: Part VIII*—Synthesis of 6, 7-Dimethoxy-3-Alkyl-Isocoumarins

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Pyridine catalysed reactions of 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid with acetic and propionic anhydrides at room temperature gave 4-acetyl- and 4-propionyl-6,7-dimethoxyisochroman-1,3-diones respectively and at boiling water bath temperature gave 3-methyl- and 3-ethyl-4-carboxy-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarins respectively, along with other products. The rearrangement of the acetyl and propionylisochromanones to the 3-methyl- and 3-ethyl-4-carboxyisocoumarins respectively, was accomplished with H_2SO_4 . The study of the various other reactions have led to the synthesis of 6,7-dimethoxy-3-alkylisocoumarins and 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins and also of 2-carboxy-4,5-dimethoxybenzyl alkyl ketones in good yields.

Previously we have reported^{1,2}, the synthesis of isocoumarins by the pyridine catalysed reaction of homophthalic acids with acetic and propionic anhydrides. We now describe the extension of these reactions to 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid³ (I) to produce 6,7-dimethoxy-3-alkylisocoumarins and 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins which are interesting as many naturally occurring isocoumarins known are 3-methylisocoumarin derivatives with $-OCH_3$ or $-OH$ substituents in the benzene ring e.g., Reticulol⁴, Oospalactone⁵ etc. 4,5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (I) with acetic and propionic anhydrides in the presence of pyridine at room temperature gave 4-acetyl- and 4-propionyl-6,7-dimethoxy-isochroman-1,3-diones IIa and IIb respectively in quantitative yields. The diones IIa and IIb isomerised on keeping with H_2SO_4 (80%) at 0–10° to give the 4-carboxyisocoumarins IIIa and IIIb ($R_1 = COOH$) respectively. At higher temperature decarboxylation took place and thus at 90–95°, the major products isolated were IIIa and IIIb ($R_1 = H$) respectively. Pyridine catalysed reaction of I with acetic anhydride at boiling water bath temperature gave the 4-carboxyisocoumarin IIIa ($R_1 = COOH$) together with the 4-acetylisocoumarin IIIa ($R_1 = COMe$) and a naphthoisocoumarin IVa, while in the reaction of I with propionic anhydride under the same conditions IIIb ($R_1 = COOH$) was isolated as the major product together with a

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small amount of the naphthoisocoumarin IVb, but no 4-propionylisocoumarin derivative was isolated. The constitutions of IVa and IVb are assigned on the basis of elemental analysis and by analogy to the earlier observation^{1,2}.

The isocoumarin IIIa ($R_1 = H$) with aq. NaOH gave the ketone Va and the same ketone was obtained by refluxing IIa, IIIa ($R_1 = COOH$) and IIIa ($R_1 = COMe$). This can be expected as the intermediate that would be formed in case of IIa and IIIa ($R_1 = COOH$) by opening of the ring is same and is a β -keto acid derivative which suffers ready decarboxylation to give Va. In case of IIIa ($R_1 = COMe$), the opening of the lactone ring gives acetyl acetone derivative which suffers the cleavage of the acetyl group in the presence of alkali to give Va. In the same manner IIIb ($R_1 = H$) and IIIb ($R_1 = COOH$) and IIb on refluxing with aq. NaOH gave the same ketone Vb. The ketones Va and Vb on keeping with H_2SO_4 got cyclodehydrated to give the isocoumarins IIIa and IIIb ($R_1 = H$) respectively and on reduction with $NaBH_4$ in methanolic solution followed by acidification gave the corresponding dihydroisocoumarins VIa and VIb respectively. The best routes that can be suggested for synthesis of 4-carboxy-3-alkyl- and 3-alkyl-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarins (III, $R_1 = COOH$) and (III, $R_1 = H$); are as follows :

The various reactions described support the constitutions assigned and these are also in analogy with those observed for similar isocoumarins described earlier^{1,2}. U.V. absorption values recorded for the various isocoumarin derivatives are also in good agreement with those of the similar isocoumarins^{1,2,6}. I.R. spectrum (KBr pellet) of IIIa ($R_1 = COMe$) shows characteristic absorption bands at 1722 (shoulder) and 1715 cm^{-1} (lactonic $>C=O$), and at 1688 cm^{-1} (CO of $-CO-Me$).

The mechanism for the formation of the 4-acylisochromandiones (e.g. II) and their isomerisation to 4-carboxy-3-alkyl-isocoumarins (e.g., III, $R_1 = \text{COOH}$) is discussed in the earlier publication¹. We now suggest the following mechanism on the same lines for the formation of 4-acetyl-3-methylisocoumarins (e.g., IIIa, $R_1 = \text{COMe}$) obtained in the present and previous work¹ in the pyridine catalysed reaction of homophthalic acids with Ac_2O at boiling water bath temperature (see mechanism)

MECHANISM

The formation of the 4-acetyl-3-methylisocoumarin may be taking place by further acetylation of the 4-acetylisochromandione that is initially formed and the diacetylisochromandione thus formed gets rearranged due to the presence of $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH}^+$ ions in the solution. The rearrangement may be taking place by one or both possible ways shown with simultaneous decarboxylation

The present and previous work^{1,2} shows that pyridine catalysed reaction of homophthalic acids with acetic anhydride proceed well compared to that with propionic anhydride. This may be due to higher electrophilic reactivity of MeCO^+ as compared to that of EtC^+O . It is also noted that 4-propionyl-3-ethylisocoumarin derivative was not isolated in the pyridine catalysed reaction of any homophthalic acid with propionic anhydride at boiling water bath temperature though, 4-acetyl-3-methylisocoumarin derivative is always obtained in the reaction with acetic anhydride under the similar conditions

EXPERIMENTAL

Action of acetic anhydride on 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (I) in the presence of pyridine

i) at room temperature (28–30°): 4-Acetyl-6,7-dimethoxyisochroman-1,3-dione (IIa): To a magnetically stirred mixture of acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and dry pyridine (2 ml.), 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid³ (I) (2 g.) was added in small lots within 20 minutes. More of acetic anhydride (2 ml.) was added and the stirring was continued. The acid dissolved

slowly and after some time a solid slowly separated. Dry ether (12–14 ml.) was then added and the stirring was continued for 2.5 hrs. The product was filtered, washed free of pyridine with dry ether, dried in vacuum and crystallised from chloroform as shining plates, m.p. 208–10° (decomp.). Yield 1.5 g. (crude yield 1.75 g.) (Found : C, 59.1, H, 5.0; $C_{13}H_{12}O_6$ requires, C, 59.1; H, 4.5%). The compound is insoluble in aq. $NaHCO_3$ and gives no colour with aq. or ethanolic $FeCl_3$. It decomposes slowly on keeping.

ii) at boiling water bath temperature : 4-Carboxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = COOH$), 4-acetyl-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = COMe$) and 8-acetyl-7-methyl-4,5,10,11-tetramethoxynaphtho (1,2-c) isocoumarin (IVa) : A mixture of the acid (I) (2 g.), acetic anhydride (7 ml.) and dry pyridine (3 ml.) was heated on a boiling water bath for 2 hrs under anhydrous conditions. It was poured in cold water (80 ml.) acidulated with conc. HCl (10 ml.). The sticky solid that separated on standing overnight was dissolved in hot benzene containing little ethanol (Solution A). The supernatant aqueous layer was extracted with ethyl acetate. The benzene solution 'A' and so also the ethyl acetate extract were separately and repeatedly shaken with aq. $NaHCO_3$ (in all 20 ml. each), the extracts were combined, washed with benzene and acidified (conc. HCl) when 4-carboxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = COOH$) separated as yellow solid. It crystallised from water as colourless needles, m.p. 270–73°. Yield 0.09 g. Recrystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 274–75° (blackens at 270°). (Found : C, 59.4, H, 4.7; $C_{13}H_{12}O_6$ requires : C, 59.1; H, 4.5%). U.V. absorption λ_{MeOH}^{max} 244, 280, 330 $m\mu$. (log ϵ , 4.58, 3.9, 3.53).

The benzene solution 'A' was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to small bulk (10–12 ml.) when on keeping aside for several hours pink coloured crystals of 8-acetyl-7-methyl-4,5,10,11-tetramethoxynaphtho-(1,2-c)-isocoumarin (IVa) separated. Crude yield 0.28 g., m.p. 274–78°. It crystallised from benzene as buff coloured needles, m.p. 278–80°. (Found : C, 68.3; H, 5.1; $C_{24}H_{22}O_7$ requires : C, 68.2; H, 5.2%).

The benzene mother liquor (of the solution A) was evaporated off, the residue extracted in boiling ligroin (80–100°) (50 ml.) and extract was concentrated (8–10 ml.) when 4-acetyl-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = COMe$) separated as crystalline solid. Crude yield 0.04 g., m.p. 137–42°. Recrystallised from benzene-petrol ether (40–60°) as colourless needles, m.p. 145–47° (Found : C, 64.3; H, 5.5; $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires : C, 64.1; H, 5.3%). I.R. absorption (nujol mull) 1722 (shoulder), 1715, 1688, 1632, 1608, 1568 and 1511 cm^{-1} .

Rearrangement of the isochromandione (IIa) with sulphuric acid (80%) : 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = H$) and 4-carboxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = COOH$).

i) at 0–10° : The isochromandione (IIa) (0.2 g.) was added in small portions with shaking to H_2SO_4 (80%, 1.3 ml.) cooled in ice bath and shaking continued till a clear solution resulted. It was left in refrigerator overnight, poured on crushed ice and the product was triturated with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and filtered.

The insoluble residue on crystallisation from petrol ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture yielded the isocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = H$) as colourless needles, m.p. 128–30°. Yield 0.02 g. Recrystallisation from benzene-petrol ether (40–60°) gave needles, m.p. 130–31°. (Found :

C, 65.2; H, 5.4; $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires : C, 65.4; H, 5.4%. U.V. absorption : λ_{MeQH}^{max} 242, 278, 329 m μ . (log ϵ , 4.58, 3.99, 3.68).

The aq. $NaHCO_3$ filtrate on acidification gave the 4-carboxyisocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = COOH$) as white solid. Crude yield 0.135 g. It crystallised from water or ethyl acetate as colourless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 274–75° (blackens at 270°) (0.11 g.).

ii) at 90–95° : The dione (*IIa*), (0.2 g.) and H_2SO_4 (2 ml., 80%) were heated on water bath (90–95°) for an hour and the reaction worked up as above when the same two substances were obtained viz., the isocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = H$) (m.p. 130–31°, yield 0.085 g. crystallised) and 4-carboxyisocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = COOH$), (m.p. 274–75°, yield 0.025 g. crystallised). Mixed m.p. with the previous specimens showed no lowering.

Decarboxylation of the 4-carboxyisocoumarin (IIIa, $R_1 = COOH$) : The isocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = H$) : The isocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = COOH$) (0.2 g.) was heated in a metal bath at 285° for half an hour (evolution of CO_2). After triturating with aq. $NaHCO_3$ the residue was crystallised from petrol ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture when the isocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = H$) separated as needles, m.p. 128–30°. Yield 0.035 g. Recrystallisation from benzene-petrol ether (40–60°) gave colourless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 130–31°.

2-Carboxy-4,5-dimethoxybenzyl methyl ketone (Va) : (i) The isochromandione (*IIa*) (1 g.) with aq. $NaOH$ (20 ml., 10%) was refluxed for 2 hrs, cooled and acidified with conc. HCl (evolution of CO_2). The solid product crystallised from water or dil. $MeOH$ as silky needles, m.p. 192–93°. Yield 0.7 g. (crude yield 0.78 g.). (Found : C, 60.2; H, 6.0; $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ requires : C, 60.5; H, 6.1%).

(ii) A solution of the 4-carboxyisocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = COOH$) (0.2 g.) in aq. $NaOH$ (4 mls., 10%) was heated under reflux for one and half hrs, cooled and acidified (evolution of CO_2). The solid that separated was crystallised from water as needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 192–93°. Yield 0.12 g.

Cyclodehydration of the ketone (Va) : 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-methyl-isocoumarin (*IIIa*, $R_1 = H$) : The ketone (*Va*) (0.5 g.) mixed with H_2SO_4 (1.5, 90%) was kept overnight at room temperature and then poured on crushed ice. The solid product was washed with aq. $NaHCO_3$ (by trituration) and then crystallised from petrol ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture as needles, m.p. 128–30°. Yield 0.35 g. Recrystallisation from benzene-petrol ether gave needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 130–31°.

($\pm$)6,7-Dimethoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (*VIa*) : To the methanolic solution of the ketone (*Va*) (0.5 g. in 10 ml.), sodium borohydride (0.35 g.) was added in small portions with shaking and was kept aside for 2 hrs with frequent shaking. It was then acidified, diluted with water (40 ml.) and extracted repeatedly with chloroform. The extract was washed with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and then with water and after drying, the solvent was removed and the residue on trituration with cold petrol ether gave a colourless solid. (Crude yield (0.34 g., m.p. 102–04°). It crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture as

colourless needles, m.p. 104–05° (0.29 g.) (Found : C, 64.7; H, 6.2; $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires : C, 64.8; H, 6.3%). U. V. absorption : λ_{MeOH}^{max} 225, 265, 302 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.49, 4.01, 3.68).

Action of propionic anhydride on the homophthalic acid (I) in the presence of pyridine.

i) *at room temperature* : 4-Propionyl-6,7-dimethoxyisochroman-1,3-dione (IIb): The acid (I) (2 g.) was added in portions to a magnetically stirred mixture of propionic anhydride (8 ml.) and dry pyridine (2.5 ml.); protected from moisture. More of propionic anhydride (2 ml.) was then added. The acid dissolved first and then a yellow solid separated. After adding dry ether (12–14 ml.) (to facilitate stirring) stirring was continued for two and half hours and the product was filtered under suction. It was washed successively with dry ether, dil. HCl (20 ml., 2*N*, trituration) and water and then dried in vacuum. Crude yield 1.4 g., m.p. 132–35°. It crystallised from benzene-petrol ether (40–60°) in pale yellow needles, m.p. 136–37° (1.1 g.) (Found : C, 60.8; H, 5.1; $C_{14}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 60.4; H, 5.0%). The substance dissolves in aq. $NaHCO_3$ with effervescence and gives green colouration with ethanolic $FeCl_3$. It decomposes on keeping.

ii) *at boiling water bath temperature*. 4-Carboxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3-ethylisocoumarin (IIIb, $R_1 = COOH$) and 8-propionyl-7-ethyl-4,5,10,11-tetramethoxynaphtho (1,2-c) isocoumarin (IVb) : A mixture of the acid (I) (2 g.), propionic anhydride (6 ml.) and dry pyridine (2.5 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath for 2 hrs under anhydrous conditions, then poured in cold water (70 ml.) acidulated with HCl (7–8 ml.) and left overnight. The sticky solid product was dissolved in benzene (drops of ethanol) while the supernatant aq. layer was extracted with ethyl acetate. The benzene solution and also the ethyl acetate extract were shaken with aq. $NaHCO_3$ (in all 17 ml. each), the alkali extracts were combined and acidified when 4-carboxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3-ethylisocoumarin (IIIb, $R_1 = COOH$), separated as yellow solid. It was crystallised from water (charcoal) as needles, m.p. 255–58°. Yield 0.05 g. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate gave colourless needles, m.p. 258–60° (Found : C, 60.8; H, 4.9; $C_{14}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 60.4; H, 5.0%). U.V. absorption : λ_{MeOH}^{max} 246, 280, 322 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.61, 3.78, 3.47).

The benzene solution was washed well with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to a small bulk when 8-propionyl-7-ethyl-4,5,10,11-tetramethoxynaphtho (1,2-c) isocoumarin (IVb) separated as crystalline solid on standing for several hours, crude yield 0.17 g., m.p. 247–52°. It was recrystallised from benzene as pale yellow needles, m.p. 255–57°. (Found : C, 69.7; H, 5.5; $C_{26}H_{26}O_7$ requires, C, 69.3; H, 5.8%).

No other product could be isolated from the reaction.

Rearrangement of the isochromandione (IIb) with sulphuric acid (80%) : 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-ethylisocoumarin (IIIb, $R_1 = H$) and 4-carboxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3-ethylisocoumarin (IIIb, $R_1 = COOH$);

i) *at 0–10°* : The reaction of the dione (IIb) (0.2 g.) with H_2SO_4 (1 ml., 80%) was carried in the same manner as described under rearrangement of the dione IIa. The crude solid product on trituration with aq. $NaHCO_3$ gave, 6,7-dimethoxy-3-ethylisocoumarin as insoluble substance which was crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture (twice) as needles, m.p. 163–64°. Yield 0.04 g. (Found : C, 66.4; H, 5.9; $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires

C, 66.7; H, 6.0%). U.V. absorption: $\lambda_{M,OH}^{max}$ 243, 278, 330 m μ (log ϵ , 4.64, 3.99, 3.71). The aq. NaHCO₃ solution on acidification gave 4-carboxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3-ethylisocoumarin as white solid. Yield 0.07 g., m.p. 245–50°. It was crystallised from water or ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 258–60°.

ii) at 90–95°: The above reaction was carried out by heating at (90–95°) for 45 mins., the same two products were obtained but in different yields. (IIb, R₁ = H), 0.08 g. (crystallised) and (IIIb, R₁ = COOH), 0.02 g. (crystallised). Mixed m.p.'s, with the respective previous specimens were undepressed.

Decarboxylation of the 4-carboxyisocoumarin (IIIb, R₁ = COOH) The isocoumarin (IIIb, R₁ = H): The isocoumarin (IIIb, R₁ = COOH) (0.2 g.) was heated in a metal bath at 270° for 35 mins. (evolution of CO₂). The residual contents were washed with aq. NaHCO₃ (by trituration) and repeatedly crystallised from petrol ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture as colourless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 163–64° (0.045 g.).

2-Carboxy-4,5-dimethoxybenzyl methyl ketone (Vb): (i) The isochromanone (IIb) (1 g.) and aq. NaOH (20 ml., 10%) were refluxed together for 2 hrs, cooled and acidified with conc. HCl when a crystalline solid separated with evolution of CO₂. Crude yield 0.83 g., m.p. 188–91°. On crystallisation from water or dil. methanol it separated as silky needles, m.p. 196–97°. Yield 0.75 g. (Found: C, 61.8; H, 6.4; C₁₃H₁₆O₅ requires C, 61.9; H, 6.3%).

(ii) The same ketone was also obtained by treating the 4-carboxy-isocoumarin (IIIb, R₁ = COOH) (0.2 g.) with aq. NaOH (4 ml., 10%) under the same conditions. Yield 0.13 g. (crystallised), m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 196–97°.

Cyclodehydration of the ketone (Vb) 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-ethyl-isocoumarin (IIIb, R₁ = H): The ketone (Vb) (0.5 g.) was mixed with H₂SO₄ (1.5 ml., 90%) and left overnight at room temperature. The dark green solution was poured on crushed ice, the solid product was washed with aq. NaHCO₃ (trituration), dried on water bath and was crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture as colourless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 163–64°. Yield 0.36 g.

(±)-6,7-Dimethoxy-3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIb): To the methanolic solution of the ketone (Vb) (0.5 g., in 14 ml.) sodium borohydride (0.38 g.) was added in small portions and the mixture was left aside for 2 hrs with occasional shaking. It was then acidified, diluted with excess water (50 ml.) and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed successively with aq. NaHCO₃ and water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to dryness. The residual contents on trituration with cold light petrol ether furnished a solid, m.p. 82–84°. Yield 0.35 g. It crystallised from petrol ether (60–80°)-acetone mixture as colourless needles, m.p. 86–87° (Found: C, 66.6; H, 7.1; C₁₃H₁₆O₄ requires: C, 66.1; H, 6.8%). U.V. absorption: $\lambda_{M,OH}^{max}$ 224, 265, 302 m μ (log ϵ , 4.44, 4.0, 3.77).

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